

C O N C L U S I O N S

To sum up the experience gathered in the preparation of a solution of this gum and its purification is that fresh samples obtained in the semi-solid state from the plant are the best to work with. When samples become dried up in air and become old they undergo marked decrease in solubility and the yield of the precipitated gum is also small. If the sample is fresh and soft, the purified gum obtained after precipitation by alcohol is fairly white in colour and the colour does not change easily. The aqueous solution from a white specimen of the purified gum is also colourless.

Soft and fresh samples of the gum, directly collected from a plant in the month of October after the rains were over (in Bengal), were therefore always used in the investigations recorded in subsequent parts of this series of study.

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STUDIES ON GUM JEOL (*ODINA WODIER*, ROXB.). PART II.

HYDROLYSIS AND THE REDUCING SUGARS

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Gum jeol has been hydrolysed by H_2SO_4 (conc. $<0.5N$) to yield some reducing substances and a complex acid (termed *jeolic acid*) which forms colloidal solution in water. More drastic hydrolysis of the gum with H_2SO_4 (conc. $>1.5N$) by prolonged refluxing for 16 to 18 hours yields larger amounts of reducing substances, being about 86% (calculated as glucose) of the weight of the gum. These reducing substances have been identified and characterised as *l*-arabinose and *d*-galactose.

In Part I of this series of investigations (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 25, 59) it has been observed that fresh gums, specially when collected in the semi-solid state, are readily miscible in water but, an old dry sample is only slightly miscible. This latter when kept in contact with water for a number of days gives a uniform solution. This naturally raises a question as to whether the gum in prolonged contact with water is changed by hydrolysis before passing into solution. In the present investigation an answer to this question has been attempted.

The second point investigated in this connection is the nature of the products, if the gum actually do hydrolyse in water. Gum arabic has been observed to yield (O'Sullivan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1884,45,41) on hydrolysis with H_2SO_4 , a pentose sugar (*l*-arabinose) and a relatively small amount of hexose (*d*-galactose) together with an acid which he termed the "arabic acid" and to which the molecules of arabinose and galactose were considered to be attached.

In the present investigation work on almost similar line has been pursued to isolate the hydrolysis products from gum jeol and to identify and characterise them. It has also been the object to indicate the approximate quantities of these products on the percentage basis.

EXPERIMENTAL

Gum jeol used in these experiments were purified by thrice precipitation by alcohol as recorded in Part I (*loc. cit.*).

Hydrolysis by Water.—Hydrolysis of the gum in aqueous solution on keeping was first examined. Appearance of reducing substances as products of hydrolysis was not, however, tested by Fehling's solution as the latter introduced alkali which itself might have hydrolysing effect. The hydrolysis was therefore followed by noting the change in optical rotation. The gum solution itself was observed to possess an optical activity, its specific rotation amounting to about $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +29^\circ$ (observed in 1% aqueous solution).

Aqueous solution in the cold showed no hydrolysis even when kept for a number of days. Clear evidence of hydrolysis began to appear roughly after a month's time. Warming the solution on a water-bath appeared to accelerate hydrolysis. This fact was corroborated by an examination with Fehling's solution when an immediate precipitation indicated previous hydrolysis. Fehling's solution added to the cold gum solution of the same concentration, as a control measure, failed to produce a distinct precipitate, but produced only a faint brown colour.

Hydrolysis of the gum in course of its purification by alcohol, as recorded in Part I (*loc. cit.*), was also examined by precipitation of the gum from a concentrated solution by alcohol and keeping the mixture as such for about 24 hours, after which the supernatant solution was tested with Fehling's solution. A slight but immediate precipitation confirmed previous hydrolysis. A gum solution, similarly preserved for over a month, also showed signs of hydrolysis. It was thus possible to find a clue to the solubility behaviour of some of the samples mentioned in Part I (*loc. cit.*) viz., samples 2, 3, and 4, which were found to be insoluble in the beginning but gradually went into solution when sufficient time was allowed.

Hydrolysis by Acids.—At the temperature of the water-bath vigorous and almost instantaneous reduction of Fehling's solution was noticed and a more copious precipitation, in comparison with a control in which no acid was added, confirmed the hydrolysing action of acids on this gum. A rough and qualitative

investigation revealed that perhaps hydrolysis was more vigorous with strong acids like HCl, H₂SO₄, etc. than with weak ones (CH₃COOH, C₆H₅COOH).

Hydrolysis by Alkalis.—Alkaline hydrolysis was tested in a similar manner against a control in which no alkali was added. Copious and instantaneous precipitation in a gum solution (0.3%), warmed with an equal volume of *N*/5-NaOH till the colour turned black, showed the presence of fairly strong hydrolysis in presence of alkalis.

Products of Hydrolysis

(a) *Mild Hydrolysis.*—To a clear 2% solution of the gum sufficient H₂SO₄ was added to make its concentration 0.5*N* and the mixture warmed on a water-bath for 2 hours. From the cooled solution H₂SO₄ was quantitatively removed by addition of Ba(OH)₂ and filtration. The filtrate was made up to 250 c.c. from which an aliquot part was titrated by Fehling's solution, standardised by standard glucose solution with methylene blue as an indicator. The amount of the reducing substances is expressed in terms of percentage of glucose. Results are represented in the table below.

TABLE I

Gum sample.	Amount of gum taken.	Sugar expressed as glucose		Mean.
Sample 3*	40 g.	12.01 g.	30%	30% (approx.)
Sample 4*	36	10.70	29	

Gum arabic with similar treatment yielded about 4 to 5% of reducing sugars (calc. as glucose; error $\pm 1.5\%$). Like gum arabic which on hydrolysis with 0.5*N*-H₂SO₄ yields the arabic acid (cf. Sullivan, *loc. cit.*, also Thomas and Murray, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1928, 32, 676; Pauli and Palmrich, *Kolloid Z.*, 1937, 79, 63), the gum jeol has been observed to yield besides the reducing substances an acid which will be subsequently referred to as "Jeolic acid" throughout these investigations. The hydrolysis carried out with 0.5*N*-H₂SO₄ will be similarly referred to as the *mild hydrolysis*.

The jeolic acid, thus obtained, is quite a stable compound which is always obtained whatever be the method of mild hydrolysis, followed either by prolonged heating with acids or by electro dialysis with acids†.

The jeolic acid solution thus obtained formed a colloidal solution and it was freed from the sugars by dialysis after which the acid was obtained in the solid state by precipitation with alcohol (yield 10g. from 100g. of gum). The residue was dried on a water-bath to constant weight. A known weight of this acid was then dissolved in water.

(b) *Hydrolysis of the Jeolic Acid.*—Attempts were next made to estimate the amounts of reducing substances by a complete hydrolysis of the jeolic

* (Vide Part I).

† The procedure and the result of electro dialysis will be taken up in a future communication of this series.

acid by prolonged refluxing with H_2SO_4 (conc.) $1N$). Refluxing was continued for 16 to 18 hours (cf. Heidelberger and Goebel, *J. Exp. Med.*, 1929, 49, 459). From an analogy with gum arabic it was expected that such hydrolysis would yield some reducing sugars and a hexuronic acid which is usually known to form an insoluble barium salt. The excess of H_2SO_4 and all the hexuronic acid formed were quantitatively removed by the addition of BaCO_3 at the temperature of the water-bath till the solution was neutral to litmus paper. Precipitation was completed by keeping the solution overnight, after which Ba salts were filtered off and washed thoroughly with double distilled water till free from sugars. The filtrate and the wash liquid were cooled and mixed together when the mixture presented a yellow colour. A small portion of this yellow solution was tested with dilute H_2SO_4 for any barium uronate that might have escaped precipitation. A very faint turbidity roughly indicated a practical absence of such a salt in the solution. The solution was then made up to 500 c.c., an aliquot part of which was evaporated on a water-bath when a sticky, brown substance resembling molasses in appearance and odour suggested the presence of sugars. The amount of these sugars was determined by titration with Fehling's solution. The percentage of sugars in the jeolic acid was estimated to be 82%, 84.2% and 83% in three determinations yielding a mean value of 83.06. For the sake of comparison the arabic acid, from gum arabic, which was also similarly treated, yielded sugar to the extent of 82.5%.

(c) *Total Reducing Sugars.*—From the above two stages of hydrolysis the total amount of reducing sugars in the two stages amounted to about 88.1% (expressed as glucose) of the air-dried, purified sample of gum jeol. With arabic acid the corresponding percentage was 62.1%. This figure for gum jeol was further confirmed by a direct drastic hydrolysis of a known weight of the gum with H_2SO_4 (conc.) $>1.5N$ and estimation by Fehling's solution after removal of the excess of H_2SO_4 and all of the uronic acid by BaCO_3 . Two samples of purified gum jeol yielded the following results :

(i) Gum jeol (10 g.) yielded 3.5 g. of reducing sugars (calc. as glucose), 85%.

(ii) Gum jeol (7g.) yielded 6 g. of reducing sugars (as glucose), 86%

Gum jeol thus yields much greater amounts of reducing sugars than gum arabic.

Nature of the Reducing Sugars

For examination of the products of hydrolysis it was necessary to get the substance in as much pure a state as possible. For this reason the following procedure was adopted.

Crude gum (40 g.) was dissolved in 500 c.c. of 40% H_2SO_4 solution and heated on a water-bath for 2 hours. The solution was then neutralised by CaCO_3 . The precipitate formed was filtered off and washed several times with warm water. The washings were then transferred to the filtrate which

was then concentrated to 100 c.c. under reduced pressure. Alcohol (200 c.c.) was then added when the calcium salt of the complex jeolic acid (also of aldobionic and uronic acids, if formed) separated out as a white precipitate which was filtered off. The solution was next freed from alcohol under reduced pressure to a syrupy liquid of light red colour. A part of this solution was warmed on a water-bath with resorcinol and HCl when the appearance of a red colour indicated the presence of hexose.

Pentoses were similarly detected with the help of Tollen's reagent when a red colour appeared in 2 to 3 minutes' time at the temperature of the water-bath. This was confirmed by the addition of FeCl_3 solution when the colour changed from red to green. The orcinol test was not, however, characteristic of pentoses alone but of uronic acids as well, but since uronic acid had been eliminated by formation of its Ca salt and precipitation by alcohol, the response to the test might be due to the presence of pentose alone in this case.

Characterisation of the Pentose.—A part of the syrupy mother liquor, mixed with twice its volume of methyl alcohol, was kept in the refrigerator at 0° for crystallisation. A faint turbidity appeared in about 12 hours' time. On addition of some more methyl alcohol crystals appeared in about 24 hours' time and after about 2 hours the crystallisation appeared to be complete. The good crop of crystals, thus obtained, was separated by filtration; the yield was about 0.7 g. from about 15 g. of sugar mixture, concentrated by evaporation of the mother-liquor in *vacuo* and drying at room temperature in a vacuum desiccator. The crystals were then recrystallised from methyl alcohol, m.p. was 151° at first, but was it raised to 153° and then to 155° after four crystallisations (mixed m.p. with Merck's *l*-arabinose, 154°). Specific rotation $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = +105^\circ$. Hence the product appears to be pure *l*-arabinose. It was further confirmed by converting the sugar into its osazone, m.p. 148-50°, while the m.p. of the corresponding compound of *l*-arabinose is 157°. The combustion analysis of the substance shows C, 40.1; H, 6.72; O, 53.2% (*l*-arabinose gives C, 40.0; H, 6.67; O, 53.3%). It is therefore justifiable to conclude that the sugar separated by the above procedure, and purified by repeated crystallisations from methyl alcohol is probably *l*-arabinose but the phenylosazone might be a mixture of osazone and phenylhydrazone.

Characterisation of the Hexose.—A portion of the solution obtained after separating the crystals in the above procedure was carefully evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure and the sugar present in solution recovered in the dry state by desiccation in a vacuum desiccator. This was then dissolved in minimum amount of water and treated with methyl alcohol to get rid of the pentose that might still be present. After repeating this process thrice the sugar was obtained in the dry state by evaporation and tested for its specific rotation; $[\alpha]_{\text{D}}^{25} = +78.5^\circ$ (observed in 1% aqueous solution).

A small quantity of sugar was dissolved in minimum amount of water and oxidised with 1:1 nitric acid by heating on a water-bath for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The solution was then rapidly cooled under the tap and vigorously scratched, when fine crystals began to appear. On keeping this solution overnight further amounts of the crystals appeared, but on keeping for 4 days sufficient quantities could be collected. The crystals were needle-shaped, m.p. 214-16°. This compares favourably with the m.p. of mucic acid (218). The substance was insoluble in cold water and alcohol but dissolved sparingly in boiling water from which it was purified by crystallisation. It was, however, insoluble in boiling alcohol. The aqueous solution was strongly acidic to litmus. All these properties suggest the substance to be mucic acid. It was further confirmed by converting it into its tetraacetyl derivative, m.p. 262°; the crystals are insoluble in water but readily soluble in alcohol. The melting point agrees well with that of the tetraacetyl derivative of mucic acid (m.p. 266°). This strongly indicates the presence of hexose in this case as *d*-galactose, which was finally confirmed by noting the mixed m.p. with Merck's *d*-galactose (217° sharp) (m.p. of the purified substance has been observed to be 214-216° and that of Merck's *d*-galactose, 218°).

The mother-liquor after separation of the hexose was further tested for any reducing substances that might still be left, but no such indication was obtained. Hence, the reducing substances are the two types of sugars only, viz., pentose (*L*-arabinose) and hexose (*d*-galactose). A rough estimation of the pentose by furfural reaction and of the hexose by subtracting the amount of pentose from the total amount of reducing sugars estimated by Fehling's solution shows the ratio of pentose to hexose as 1 : 1.3.

CONCLUSIONS

Both gum arabic and gum jeol yield on hydrolysis sufficient quantities of reducing sugars which are mainly *L*-arabinose and *d*-galactose. The facts that gum jeol yields about 86% of its weight of reducing sugars as compared to about 62% in the case of gum arabic on drastic hydrolysis, and that gum jeol in aqueous solution hydrolyses spontaneously show that the latter is a more complex body. But whether the difference in properties of the two gums can be attributed to the difference in their sugar contents alone will be taken up for discussion in a subsequent communication.

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